

A MATTER OF STYLE IN EDUCATION

M. Sharma* and N. Agarwal**

The present paper has many practical implications for programming and institution. By turning into individual difference practically each individual's strength, talent and style we stand to accomplish a major educational goal i.e. to help student find a 'niche' for themselves that makes them effective social member. If we accept these premises, school become a place for talent development rather than mere lesson planning.

Education is a national responsibility, which is to transform a static society into one vibrant with a commitment to development and change. The development of human resources is said to be the main function of education through which development of attitudes aptitude, capability both of knowledge and skills, provides strength and resilience to respond to changing situation. The goal of society's development are enshrined in the constitution and they envisage a society based on justice, social economic and political equality of status and opportunity and it enjoy as the state do endeavour to all citizen, fraternity assuming the dignity of the individual and the unity and integrity of nation.

Active learning or construction of knowledge entails information processing beyond passive responses to stimuli or encoding verbatim of whatever input has been provided. It also means that individuals differently and selectively attend to and process-learning materials based on their prior knowledge, understanding, values, attitudes, styles and resultant motivation. Thus, active learning is most likely when instructional programming and design take into account development and individual characteristics that have a direct bearing on how students learn and how well they learn under specific learning condition.

Our learning agreement is that school will face much better if they place the act of learning at the center of education process. An act of learning takes place when there major components of instructional setting interact with one another in such a ways to produce the intellectual or artistic equivalent of spontaneous combustion these three components are a learner, a teacher and the material to be learned i.e. curriculum.

*Reader in V.M.L.G. (P.G.) College, Ghaziabad.

**Lecturer in Institute of Management Education Sahibabad, Ghaziabad.

Each of these three components has its own important sub components. Thus, for example, when considering the learner we must look at his abilities and present appropriate levels of challenges in a particular area of study, the learner's interest in the topic and ways in which we can enhance his interest or help him to develop new interests and the preferred styles of learning that will improve the learner's motivation to pursue the materials being studied. Interest in notion of styles developed in the part as a response to the recognition that conventional ability tests provide only part of the answer to why people differ in their performance which is in anything else. If abilities are only part of the answer to understanding how and why people differ in their performance, what might the rest of the answer be?

The Concept of Style

A style is a preferred way of using one's abilities. It is not in itself an ability but rather a preference. Abilities and preference may or may not correspond as we find in the case of some one who wants to be a creative writer but who just can't come up with the ideas, styles refers to how you go about a task but ability refers to how well you do a task and the correlation between styles and abilities should be low. In Sternberg's view (1997), that correlation is often not low enough, so he makes the distinction between styles based on differing patterns of abilities basically, cognitive styles and learning styles and styles based on differing preferences for operating one way as opposed to another (thinking styles). Information processing styles also appears to be preference based. The increasing volume of published materials on styles has included a number of excellent review papers. Vernon (1973) examined the historical roots of cognitive styles in early 20th century German typological theories and then critically analyzed contemporary approaches. Bieri (1971), Goldstein and Blackman (1978), and Kagan and Kogan (1970) considered the diverse theoretical orientations that have distinguished the cognitive style domain. Kogan (1976) offered a review of research on cognitive style from the point of view of their implication for intellectual functioning and academic achievement Wardell and Royce (1978) analyzed problems, related to the definition of style in the current literature.

In the 1970's the concept of style was further developed as it gained popularity among educators. As a result, the notion of styles developed in two directions through research on educational psychology:

- ◆ Investigation attempts to apply traditional cognitive styles to school setting, seeking explanation for student's individual differences in achievement and performance via styles.
- ◆ To create new frameworks for studying learning and teaching styles based on empirical observations rather than theoretical background.
- ◆ Both successes and failures that have been attributed to abilities are often due to styles. We should give styles their proper due, if only because preference can be so much easier to mold than abilities.

Cognitive Styles :

The more specific term, cognitive refers to an individual way of processing information. The term was developed by cognitive psychologist conducting research into problem solving and sensory and perceptual abilities. Cognitive styles were described by Gardner, Holzman, Klein, Linton and Spence (1959) as developmentally stabilized Cognitive control that are relatively invariant over situations. Originally thought to be independent of ability it soon becomes clear that many styles were adaptive over a broad range of tasks especially classified as high or low on a style according to their performance in a given criterion task and then the highs are compared with lows on how they handle other tasks and characteristics. The concept of learning styles appeared around the 1970's which unlike cognitive styles was focused on educational situations where the style that was particularly influential was that of Kolb (1976) who based his model on an experimental learning theory and proposed four abilities.

- ◆ To experience
- ◆ To reflect
- ◆ To conceptualize, and
- ◆ To experiment

Our major difficulty with all such states is that they conceived as bipolar e.g. field independent Vs field dependent and as independent of context, for example, field independent individuals are said to be able to separate relevant cues from compelling, irrelevant cues and they are therefore good at finding simple figures embedded in more complex figures but manifest poor social skills, such as facial recognition. But if a style operates according to the context in which it is applied, it is no longer behaving as a general style but as something else : in this case, much more like two separate abilities.

Information Processing Styles

Another metaphor for construing the relation between the relation between the way students handle tasks and the nature of the outcome is derived from information processing. The information processing model is based on the assumption that "learning style assessed from a task-oriented process orientation is more likely to be useful than cycle orientation" (Pask (1976)

Model of learning styles might be dealt with under this heading. He found that students in classification under two :

- ◆ Testing one-limited hypotheses at a time.
- ◆ Test more complex hypotheses simultaneously.

When students habitually adopted a particularly strategy he said they exhibited a style of learning. Versatile students who switched strategy as appropriate to the task were considered versatile, but those who stuck to one style to the exclusion of the other displayed improvidence.

Constructs assessed by questionnaires deriving from information processing theory are meant to be uncontaminated by motivation, affect and context. Moreno and Divesta (1991) for example claim that information processing mechanisms are universal and culture fair a state obtained by defining item clusters from first order factor analysis, a procedure said to exclude motivational and attitudinal aspects and to access directly information processing control mechanism.

Thinking Styles

We all have a style profile, meaning we show varying amounts of each style, but we are not locked into any one profile. We can vary our style to suit different tasks and situations. For example, the style you need to discern the meaning of a work of literature is not the same one you need to read detailed directions. The style you need to solve an algebra work problem is not the one you need to construct a geometric proof. Styles further vary over the course of a lifetime and change as a result of the role models we emulate at different points in our lives, we do vary in our flexibility to shift styles, and in the strength of our preference. But while we have preferred styles, our styles are fluid not fixed.

Many theories of styles have been proposed for example, Gregore 1985, Molland 1973, Renzulli and Smith 1978, all are attempts to describe how people think. One such theory is known as mental self-government. The basic idea is that we must organize or govern ourselves, and the ways in which we do correspond to the kinds of governments and governmental branches that exist worldwide. Sternberg though it is important to separate styles from abilities. We see styles more as preference for doing things in certain way. Preference are a matter of degree not of category. So category, so that individuals may have a profile of styles, with one or more dominant. Then, individuals with a particular style can achieve well if the task allows them to use their dominant style.

Catering the Individual Difference in Education

An educational system has a aim the development of individual potential. Thus, though nature of both, individuals have a potential repertoire of talents, abilities and styles. It is education's role to help them realize those strengths and to develop their weakness thereby making them more effective and making society the richer for it. It seems reasonable that though individual difference psychologist cannot only help identify what those strengths and weakness might be, but can also develop a technology for optimizing them. It is practical to acquaint teachers with the important dimensions of individual difference so they are aware of and sensitive to them in their everyday classroom interaction with student. Hunt (1971) presented five teaching styles which were differentiated on the basis of low to high structure which allowed varying degrees of student choice and independence. The problem of identifying and measuring a

particular aptitude or thinking style was thus, obviated while still catering to educationally relevant individual differences. Sternberg (1994) has devised a number of instruments to assess style. One is based on self-report of student or teachers, another on performance and a third on evaluations by another person. One tool looks at teaching styles rather than learning styles. The most direct way is to analyze the types of instructional and assessment activities a person prefers. By doing this, teachers can make difference to their students.

CONCLUSION

Educational research from a psychological perspective is generally, directed toward a deeper understanding of teaching and learning process in everyday contexts with the ultimate intention of improving the quality and effectiveness of education. Having an effect on practice depends in part, on choosing a conceptual framework that simplifies complexity while providing descriptions of everyday experience that the participant can recognize. This implies a set of variables or analytic categories that are narrowly focused on the everyday context yet conveying an overall understanding of how learning takes place. We believe that a focus on capitalizing on and developing each child strength and talents also places the need for improved academic achievement into a larger perspective about the goal of education our vision of school for talent development grows out of the belief that everyone has an important role to play in the improvement of society and that everyone's role can be enhanced if we provide all students with the opportunity, resource and encouragement to develop their talents as fully as possible. From this point of view, the diversity of our students population is a strength rather than a weakness from this diversity come various stylistic difference an adaptation to learning task and social environments. Properly developed and used they can have high functional and adaptive value.

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